

**TOP 10 INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM
PAPERS : RECOMMENDED READING –
NETWORK SECURITY RESEARCH**

<https://wirelessnetworksecurity903000527.wordpress.com/>

AN IMPLEMENTATION OF INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM USING GENETIC ALGORITHM

Mohammad Sazzadul Hoque, Md. Abdul Mukit and Md. Abu Naser Bikas, Shahjalal University of Science and Technology, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

Nowadays it is very important to maintain a high level security to ensure safe and trusted communication of information between various organizations. But secured data communication over internet and any other network is always under threat of intrusions and misuses. So Intrusion Detection Systems have become a needful component in terms of computer and network security. There are various approaches being utilized in intrusion detections, but unfortunately any of the systems so far is not completely flawless. So, the quest of betterment continues. In this progression, here we present an Intrusion Detection System (IDS), by applying genetic algorithm (GA) to efficiently detect various types of network intrusions. Parameters and evolution processes for GA are discussed in details and implemented. This approach uses evolution theory to information evolution in order to filter the traffic data and thus reduce the complexity. To implement and measure the performance of our system we used the KDD99 benchmark dataset and obtained reasonable detection rate.

KEYWORDS

Computer & Network Security, Intrusion Detection, Intrusion Detection System, Genetic Algorithm, KDD Cup 1999 Dataset.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0312nsa08.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa12_current.html

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Botha, R. Solms, “Utilizing Neural Networks For Effective Intrusion Detection”, ISSA, 2004.
- [2] R. Graham, “FAQ: Network Intrusion Detection Systems”. March 21, 2000.
- [3] D. Zamboni, “Using Internal Sensors For Computer Intrusion Detection”. Center for Education and Research in Information Assurance and Security, Purdue University. August 2001.
- [4] K. Scarfone, P. Mell, “Guide to Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS)”. Computer Security Resource Center (National Institute of Standards and Technology). February 2007.
- [5] A. Chittur, “Model Generation for an Intrusion Detection System Using Genetic Algorithms”. January 2005.
- [6] W. Li, “Using Genetic Algorithm for Network Intrusion Detection”. “A Genetic Algorithm Approach to Network Intrusion Detection”. SANS Institute, USA, 2004.
- [7] W. Lu, I. Traore, “Detecting New Forms of Network Intrusion Using Genetic Programming”. Computational Intelligence, vol. 20, pp. 3, Blackwell Publishing, Malden, pp. 475-494, 2004.
- [8] M. M. Pillai, J. H. P. Eloff, H. S. Venter, “An Approach to Implement a Network Intrusion Detection System using Genetic Algorithms”, Proceedings of SAICSIT, pp:221-228, 2004.
- [9] S. M. Bridges, R. B. Vaughn, “Fuzzy Data Mining And Genetic Algorithms Applied To Intrusion Detection”, Proceedings of 12th Annual Canadian Information Technology Security Symposium, pp. 109-122, 2000.
- [10] J. Gomez, D. Dasgupta, “Evolving Fuzzy Classifiers for Intrusion Detection”, Proceedings of the IEEE, 2002.
- [11] M. Middlemiss, G. Dick, “Feature selection of intrusion detection data using a hybrid genetic algorithm/KNN approach”, Design and application of hybrid intelligent systems, IOS Press Amsterdam, pp.519-527, 2003.
- [12] Srinivas Mukkamala, Andrew H. Sung, Ajith Abraham, “Intrusion detection using an ensemble of intelligent paradigms”, Journal of Network and Computer Applications, Volume 28, Issue 2, April 2005, Pages 167-182
- [13] S. Peddabachigari, Ajith Abraham, C. Grosan, J. Thomas, “Modeling intrusion detection system using hybrid intelligent systems”, Journal of Network and Computer Applications, Volume 30, Issue 1, January 2007, Pages 114–132

- [14] M. Saniee Abadeh, J. Habibi, C. Lucas, “[Intrusion detection using a fuzzy genetics-based learning algorithm](#)”, Journal of Network and Computer Applications, Volume 30, Issue 1, January 2007, Pages 414-428
- [15] Tao Peng, C. Leckie, Kotagiri Ramamohanarao, “[Information sharing for distributed intrusion detection systems](#)”, Journal of Network and Computer Applications, Volume 30, Issue 3, August 2007, Pages 877–899
- [16] M. Crosbie, E. Spafford, “[Applying Genetic Programming to Intrusion Detection](#)”, Proceedings of the AAAI Fall Symposium, 1995.
- [17] T. Xia, G. Qu, S. Hariri, M. Yousif, “An Efficient Network Intrusion Detection Method Based on Information Theory and Genetic Algorithm”, Proceedings of the 24th IEEE International Performance Computing and Communications Conference (IPCCC ‘05), Phoenix, AZ, USA. 2005.
- [18] Anup Goyal, Chetan Kumar, “[GA-NIDS: A Genetic Algorithm based Network Intrusion Detection System](#)”, 2008.
- [19] R. H. Gong, M. Zulkernine, P. Abolmaesumi, “[A Software Implementation of a Genetic Algorithm Based Approach to Network Intrusion Detection](#)”, 2005. International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA), Vol.4, No.2, March 2012 119
- [20] B. Abdullah, I. Abd-alghafar, Gouda I. Salama, A. Abd-alhafez, “[Performance Evaluation of a Genetic Algorithm Based Approach to Network Intrusion Detection System](#)”, 2009.
- [21] A. Sung, S. Mukkamala, “Identifying important features for intrusion detection using support vector machines and neural networks” in Symposium on Applications and the Internet, pp. 209–216. 2003.
- [22] J. P. Planquart, “[Application of Neural Networks to Intrusion Detection](#)”, SANS Institute Reading Room.
- [23] R. G. Bace, “Intrusion Detection”, Macmillan Technical Publishing. 2000.
- [24] S. Kumar, E. Spafford, “[A Software architecture to Support Misuse Intrusion Detection](#)” in The 18th National Information Security Conference, pp. 194-204. 1995.
- [25] K. Ilgun, R. Kemmerer, P. A. Porras, “[State Transition Analysis: A Rule-Based Intrusion Detection Approach](#)”, IEEE Transaction on Software Engineering, 21(3):pp. 181-199. 1995.
- [26] S. Kumar, “[Classification and Detection of Computer Intrusions](#)”, Purdue University, 1995.

[27] V. Bobor, “Efficient Intrusion Detection System Architecture Based on Neural Networks and Genetic Algorithms”, Department of Computer and Systems Sciences, Stockholm University /Royal Institute of Technology, KTH/DSV, 2006.

[28] KDD-CUP-99 Task Description; <http://kdd.ics.uci.edu/databases/kddcup99/task.html>

[29] KDD Cup 1999: Tasks; <http://www.kdd.org/kddcup/index.php?section=1999&method=task>

[30] KDD Cup 1999: Data; <http://www.kdd.org/kddcup/index.php?section=1999&method=data>

[31] Results of the KDD’99 Classifier Learning Contest; <http://cseweb.ucsd.edu/~elkan/clresults.html>

[32] H. G. Kayacik, A. N. Zincir-Heywood, M. I. Heywood, “Selecting Features for Intrusion Detection: A Feature Relevance Analysis on KDD 99 Intrusion Detection Datasets”, May 2005.

[33] G. Folino, C. Pizzuti, G. Spezzano, “GP Ensemble for Distributed Intrusion Detection Systems”. ICAPR 54-62, 2005.

[34] Sectools.Org: 2006 Results; <http://sectools.org/tools2006.html>

[35] SecTools.Org: Top 125 Network Security Tools; <http://sectools.org/tag/ids/>

[36] Snort (software); http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snort_%28software%29

[37] InfoWorld, The greatest open source software of all time, 2009; <http://www.infoworld.com/d/open-source/greatest-open-source-software-all-time776?source=fssr>

[38] Suricata (software); [http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Suricata_\(software\)](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Suricata_(software))

[39] The Bro Network Security Monitor; <http://bro-ids.org/>

COMBINING NAIVE BAYES AND DECISION TREE FOR ADAPTIVE INTRUSION DETECTION

Dewan Md. Farid¹, Nouria Harbi¹, and Mohammad Zahidur Rahman²

¹ERIC Laboratory, University Lumière Lyon 2 – France

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Jahangirnagar University, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new learning algorithm for adaptive network intrusion detection using naive Bayesian classifier and decision tree is presented, which performs balance detections and keeps false positives at acceptable level for different types of network attacks, and eliminates redundant attributes as well as contradictory examples from training data that make the detection model complex. The proposed algorithm also addresses some difficulties of data mining such as handling continuous attribute, dealing with missing attribute values, and reducing noise in training data. Due to the large volumes of security audit data as well as the complex and dynamic properties of intrusion behaviours, several data miningbased intrusion detection techniques have been applied to network-based traffic data and host-based data in the last decades. However, there remain various issues needed to be examined towards current intrusion detection systems (IDS). We tested the performance of our proposed algorithm with existing learning algorithms by employing on the KDD99 benchmark intrusion detection dataset. The experimental results prove that the proposed algorithm achieved high detection rates (DR) and significant reduce false positives (FP) for different types of network intrusions using limited computational resources.

KEYWORDS

Decision Tree, Detection Rate, False Positive, Naive Bayesian classifier, Network Intrusion Detection

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0410ijnas2.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa10_current.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Jackson, T., Levine, J., Grizzard, J., Owen, and H., “An investigation of a compromised host on a honeynet being used to increase the security of a large enterprise network,” IEEE workshop on Information Assurance and Security, IEEE, 2004.
- [2] D. Y. Yeung, and Y. X. Ding, “Host-based intrusion detection using dynamic and static behavioral models,” Pattern Recognition, 36, 2003, pp. 229-243.
- [3] X. Xu, and T. Xie, “A reinforcement learning approach for host-based intrusion detection using sequences of system calls,” In Proc. of International Conference on Intelligent Computing, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, LNCS 3644, 2005, pp. 995-1003.
- [4] Krasser, S., Grizzard, J., Owen, H., and Levine. J., “The use of honeynets to increase computer network security and user awareness,” Journal of Security Education, vol. 1, 2005, pp. 23-37.
- [5] Shon T., Seo J., and Moon J., “SVM approach with a genetic algorithm for network intrusion detection,” in Proc. of 20th International Symposium on Computer and Information Sciences (ISCIS 2005), Berlin: Springer-Verlag, 2005, pp. 224-233.
- [6] X. Xu, X.N. Wang, “Adaptive network intrusion detection method based on PCA and support vector machines,” Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence (ADMA 2005), LNAI 3584, 2005, pp. 696-703.
- [7] Martin Roesch, “SNORT: The open source network intrusion system,” Official web page of Snort at <http://www.snort.org/>
- [8] L. C. Wu, C. H. Hung, and S. F. Chen, “Building intrusion pattern miner for snort network intrusion detection system,” Journal of Systems and Software, vol. 80, Issue 10, 2007, pp. 1699-1715.
- [9] Lazarevic, A., Ertöz, L., Kumar, V., Ozgur, A., Srivastava, and J., “A comparative study of anomaly detection schemes in network intrusion” International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA), Volume 2, Number 2, April 2010 23
- [12] Lee W., “A data mining and CIDF based approach for detecting novel and distributed intrusions,” Recent Advances in Intrusion Detection, 3rd International Workshop, RAID 2000, Toulouse, France, October 2-4, 2000, Proc. Lecture Notes in Computer Science 1907 Springer, 2000, pp. 49-65.
- [13] Lee W., Stolfo S., and Mok K., “Adaptive Intrusion Detection: A Data Mining Approach,” Artificial Intelligence Review, 14(6), December 2000, pp. 533-567.
- [14] Stolfo J., Fan W., Lee W., Prodromidis A., and Chan P.K., “Cost-based modeling and evaluation for data mining with application to fraud and intrusion detection,” DARPA Information Survivability Conference, 2000.

- [15] N.B. Amor, S. Benferhat, and Z. Elouedi, “[Naïve Bayes vs. decision trees in intrusion detection systems](#),” In Proc. of 2004 ACM Symposium on Applied Computing, 2004, pp. 420-424.
- [16] Mukkamala S., Janoski G., and Sung A.H., “[Intrusion detection using neural networks and support vector machines](#),” In Proc. of the IEEE International Joint Conference on Neural Networks, 2002, pp.1702-1707.
- [17] J. Luo, and S.M. Bridges, “[Mining fuzzy association rules and fuzzy frequency episodes for intrusion detection](#),” International Journal of Intelligent Systems, John Wiley & Sons, vol. 15, no. 8, 2000, pp. 687-703.
- [18] YU Yan, and Huang Hao, “[An ensemble approach to intrusion detection based on improved multi-objective genetic algorithm](#),” Journal of Software, vol. 18, no. 6, June 2007, pp. 1369-1378.
- [19] Karen Scarfone, and Peter Mell, “[Guide to intrusion detection and prevention systems \(IDPS\)](#),” National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD 20899-8930, NIST Special Publication 800-94, February, 2007.
- [20] Wasniowski R., “[Multi-sensor agent-based intrusion detection system](#),” In Proc. of the 2nd Annual Conference on Information Security, Kennesaw, Georgia, 2005, pp. 100-103.
- [21] Diego Zamboni, “[Using internal sensors for computer intrusion detection](#),” Ph.D. dissertation, Purdue University, 2001.
- [22] T. Bass, “[Intrusion detection systems and multi-sensor data fusion](#),” Communications of the ACM, 43(4), 2000, pp. 99-105.
- [23] F. Provost, and T. Fawcett, “[Robust classification for imprecise environment](#),” Machine Learning, vol. 42/3, 2001, pp. 203-231.
- [24] M. Joshi, V. Kumar, and R. Agarwal, “[Evaluating boosting algorithms to classify rare classes: Comparison and Improvements](#),” In Proc. of the 1st IEEE conference on Data Mining, San Jose, CA, 2001.
- [25] M. Joshi, R. Agarwal, and V. Kumar, “[Predicting rare classes: can boosting make any weak learner stronger?](#),” in Proc. of 8th ACM Conference ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, Edmonton, Canada, 2002.
- [26] G. Helmer, J.S.K. Wong, V. Honavar, and L. Miller, “[Automated discovery of concise predictive rules for intrusion detection](#),” Journal of Systems and Software, vol. 60, no. 3, 2002, pp. 165-175.

- [27] R.C. Chen, and S.P. Chen, "Intrusion detection using a hybrid support vector machine based on entropy and TF-IDF," International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information, and Control (IJICIC), vol. 4, no. 2, 2008, pp. 413-424.
- [28] R. Agarwal, and M.V. Joshi, "PNrule: a new framework for learning classifier models in data mining (a case-study in network intrusion detection)," Proceedings of 1st SIAM Conference on Data Mining, 2001. International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA), Volume 2, Number 2, April 2010 24
- [29] Radtke PVW, Sabourin R, and Wong T, "Intelligent feature extraction for ensemble of classifiers," In Proc. of 8th International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR 2005), Seoul: IEEE Computer Society, 2005, pp. 866-870.
- [30] R. Rifkin, A. Klautau, "In defense of one-vs-all classification," Journal of Machine Learning Research, 5, 2004, pp. 143-151.
- [31] Chebrolu S., Abraham A., and Thomas J.P., "Feature deduction and ensemble design of intrusion detection systems," Computer & Security, 24(4), 2004, pp. 295-307.
- [32] Tsymbal A., Puuronen S., Patterson D.W., "Ensemble feature selection with the simple Bayesian classification," Information Fusion, 4(2), 2003, pp. 87-100.
- [33] Sung A.H., and Mukkamala S., "Identifying important features for intrusion detection using support vector machines and neural networks," In Proc. of International Symposium on Applications and the Internet (SAINT 2003), 2003, pp. 209-217.
- [34] Oliveira LS, Sabourin R, Bortolozzi RF, and Suen CY, "Feature selection using multi-objective genetic algorithms for handwritten digit recognition," In Proc. of 16th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR 2002), Quebec: IEEE Computer Society, 2002, pp. 568-571.
- [35] Mukkamala S., and Sung A.H., "Identifying key features for intrusion detection using neural networks," In Proc. of the ICC International Conference on Computer Communications, 2002.
- [36] Lee WK, and Stolfo SJ, "A framework for constructing features and models for intrusion detection systems," ACM Transactions on Information and System Security, 3(4), 2000, pp. 227-261.
- [37] The KDD Archive. KDD99 cup dataset, 1999. <http://kdd.ics.uci.edu/databases/kddcup99/kddcup99.html>
- [38] M. Tavallaee, E. Bagheri, W. Lu, and A. Ghorbani, "A Detailed Analysis of the KDD CUP 99 Data Set," Submitted to Second IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence for Security and Defense Applications (CISDA) 2009.

- [39] J. McHugh, "Testing intrusion detection systems: a critique of the 1998 and 1999 darpa intrusion detection system evaluations as performed by Lincoln laboratory," ACM Transactions on Information and System Security, vol. 3. Np. 4, 2000, pp. 262-294.
- [40] James P. Anderson, "Computer security threat monitoring and surveillance," Technical Report 98-17, James P. Anderson Co., Fort Washington, Pennsylvania, USA, April 1980.
- [41] Dorothy E. Denning, "An intrusion detection model," IEEE Transaction on Software Engineering, SE-13(2), 1987, pp. 222-232.
- [42] Dorothy E. Denning, and P.G. Neumann "Requirement and model for IDES- A real-time intrusion detection system," Computer Science Laboratory, SRI International, Menlo Park, CA 94025-3493, Technical Report # 83F83-01-00, 1985.
- [43] S.E. Smaha, and Haystack, "An intrusion detection system," in Proc. of the IEEE Fourth Aerospace Computer Security Applications Conference, Orlando, FL, 1988, pp. 37-44.
- [44] S. Forrest, S.A. Hofmeyr, A. Somayaji, T.A. Longstaff, "A sense of self for Unix processes," in Proc. of the IEEE Symposium on Research in Security and Privacy, Oakland, CA, USA, 1996, pp. 120-128.
- [45] A. Valdes, K. Skinner, "Adaptive model-based monitoring for cyber attack detection," in Recent Advances in Intrusion Detection Toulouse, France, 2000, pp. 80-92.
- [46] C. Kruegel, D. Mutz, W. Robertson, F. Valeur, "Bayesian event classification for intrusion detection," in Proc. of the 19th Annual Computer Security Applications Conference, Las Vegas, NV, 2003. International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA), Volume 2, Number 2, April 2010 25
- [47] M.L. Shyu, S.C. Chen, K. Sarinnapakorn, L. Chang, "A novel anomaly detection scheme based on principal component classifier," in Proc. of the IEEE Foundations and New Directions of Data Mining Workshop, Melbourne, FL, USA, 2003, pp. 172-179.
- [48] W. Lee, S.J. Stolfo, "Data mining approaches for intrusion detection," In Proc. of the 7th USENIX Security Symposium (SECURITY-98), Berkeley, CA, USA, 1998, pp. 79-94.
- [49] J.E. Dickerson, J.A. Dickerson, "Fuzzy network profiling for intrusion detection," In Proc. of the 19th International Conference of the North American Fuzzy Information Processing Society (NAFIPS), Atlanta, GA, 2000, pp. 301-306.
- [50] M. Ramadas, S.O.B. Tjaden, "Detecting anomalous network traffic with self-organizing maps," In Proc. of the 6th International Symposium on Recent Advances in Intrusion Detection, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, 2003, pp. 36-54.

USING ROUGH SET AND SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE FOR NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION

Rung-Ching Chen¹, Kai-Fan Cheng² and Chia-Fen Hsieh³

¹ Department of Information Management Chaoyang University of Technology
Taichung Country, Taiwan, R.O.C

² Department of Information Management Chaoyang University of Technology
Taichung Country, Taiwan, R.O.C

³ Department of Information Management Chaoyang University of Technology
Taichung Country, Taiwan, R.O.C

ABSTRACT

The main function of IDS (Intrusion Detection System) is to protect the system, analyze and predict the behaviors of users. Then these behaviors will be considered an attack or a normal behavior. Though IDS has been developed for many years, the large number of return alert messages makes managers maintain system inefficiently. In this paper, we use RST (Rough Set Theory) and SVM (Support Vector Machine) to detect intrusions. First, RST is used to preprocess the data and reduce the dimensions. Next, the features were selected by RST will be sent to SVM model to learn and test respectively. The method is effective to decrease the space density of data. The experiments will compare the results with different methods and show RST and SVM schema could improve the false positive rate and accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Rough Set; Support Vector Machine; Intrusion Detection System; Attack Detection Rate;

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0409s1.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/current.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Agarwal and M.V. Joshi, “PNrule: a new framework for learning classifier models in data mining (a case-study in network intrusion detection),” Proceedings of First SIAM Conference on Data Mining, 2001.
- [2] B. Balajinath, and S. V. Raghavan, **Intrusion Detection Through Learning Behavior Model**. *Computer Communications* vol. 24, pp.1202-1212, 2001, 2001.
- [3] C. Chang and C. J. Lin, **LIBSVM — A Library for Support Vector Machines**.
- [4] G. Helmer, J.S.K. Wong, V. Honavar, and L. Miller, “Automated discovery of concise predictive rules for intrusion detection”, *Journal of Systems and Software*, Vol. 60, Issue 3, pp. 165–175, 2002.
- [5] C. L. Huang and W. C. Tang, The Application of Genetic Algorithm to Attribute Selection and Discretization for Rough Set Theory. Information Management Thesis, Hua Fan University Taiwan, 2003.
- [6] D. Y. Yeung and Y. Ding, **Host-based intrusion detection using dynamic and static behavioral models**. *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 36, pp. 229-243, 2003.
- [7] Guide of LIBSVM. <http://www.csie.ntu.edu.tw/~cjlin/papers/guide/guide.pdf>
- [8] L. C. Wu, C. H. Hung and S. F. Chen, **Building Intrusion Pattern Miner for Snort Network Intrusion Detection System**. *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 80, Issue 10, pp. 1699-1715, 2007.
- [9] MIT, http://www.ll.mit.edu/IST/ideval/data/1998/1998_data_index.html, 2008.
- [10] N. Toosi and M. Kahani, **A New Approach to Intrusion detection Based on An Evolutionary Soft Computing Model Using Neuro-Fuzzy Classifiers**. *Computer Communications*, vol. 30, Issue 10, pp. 2201-2212, 2007.
- [11] O. Depren, M. Topallar, E. Anarim and M. K. Ciliz, **An Intelligent Intrusion Detection System (IDS) for Anomaly and Misuse Detection in Computer Networks**. *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 29, pp. 713-722, 2005.
- [12] R. C. Chen and S. P. Chen, **Intrusion Detection Using a Hybrid Support Vector Machine Based on Entropy and TF-IDF**. *International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information and Control (IJICIC)* Vol. 4, Number 2, pp. 413-424, 2008.
- [13] S. Rubin, S. Jha, and B. Miller, **Automatic Generation and Analysis of NIDS Attacks**. Proceedings of 20th Annual Computer Security Application Conference, IEEE Computer Society, vol. 00, pp. 28-38, 2004.

[14] W. T. Wong and Y. C. Chang, A Hybrid Approach of Rough Set Theory and Genetic Algorithm for SVM-based Intrusion Detection. Information Management Thesis, Chung Hua University Taiwan, 2005.

[15] Z. Pawlak, Rough Sets, International Journal of Computer and Information Sciences, vol. 11, pp. 341-256, 1982.

[16] Z. Zhang and H. Shen, [Application of Online-training SVMs for Real-time Intrusion Detection with Different Considerations](#). Computer Communications, vol. 28, pp. 1428-1442, 2005

HIERARCHICAL DESIGN BASED INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM FOR WIRELESS AD HOC SENSOR NETWORK

Mohammad Saiful Islam Mamun¹ and A.F.M. Sultanul Kabir²

¹Department of Computer Science, Stamford University Bangladesh, 51, Siddeshwari, Dhaka.

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, American International University Bangladesh, Dhaka.

ABSTRACT

In recent years, wireless ad hoc sensor network becomes popular both in civil and military jobs. However, security is one of the significant challenges for sensor network because of their deployment in open and unprotected environment. As cryptographic mechanism is not enough to protect sensor network from external attacks, intrusion detection system needs to be introduced. Though intrusion prevention mechanism is one of the major and efficient methods against attacks, but there might be some attacks for which prevention method is not known. Besides preventing the system from some known attacks, intrusion detection system gather necessary information related to attack technique and help in the development of intrusion prevention system. In addition to reviewing the present attacks available in wireless sensor network this paper examines the current efforts to intrusion detection system against wireless sensor network. In this paper we propose a hierarchical architectural design based intrusion detection system that fits the current demands and restrictions of wireless ad hoc sensor network. In this proposed intrusion detection system architecture we followed clustering mechanism to build a four level hierarchical network which enhances network scalability to large geographical area and use both anomaly and misuse detection techniques for intrusion detection. We introduce policy based detection mechanism as well as intrusion response together with GSM cell concept for intrusion detection architecture.

KEYWORDS

WSN, IDS, Hierarchical Design, Security

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0710ijnasa07.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa10_current.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Chong Eik Loo, Mun Yong Ng, Christopher Leckie, Marimuthu Palaniswami. **Intrusion Detection for Routing Attacks in Sensor Networks**, International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks, Volume 2, Issue 4 December 2006, pages 313 – 332 DOI: 10.1080/15501320600692044,
- [2] S. Doumit and D.P. Agrawal, “**Self-organized criticality & stochastic learning based intrusion detection system for wireless sensor network**”, MILCOM 2003 – IEEE Military Communications Conference, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 609-614, 2003
- [3]. C.-C. Su, K.-M. Chang, Y.-H. Kuo, and M.- F. Horng, “**The new intrusion prevention and detection approaches for clustering-based sensor networks**”, in 2005 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference, WCNC 2005: Broadband Wirelss for the Masses -Ready for Take-off, Mar 13-17 2005.
- [4]. A. Agah, S. Das, K. Basu, and M. Asadi, “**Intrusion detection in sensor networks: A noncooperative game approach**”, in 3rd IEEE International Symposium on Network Computing and Applications, (NCA 2004), Boston, MA, August 2004, pp. 343346.
- [5]. A. da Silva, M. Martins, B. Rocha, A. Loureiro, L. Ruiz, and H. Wong, “**Decentralized intrusion detection in wireless sensor networks**”, Proceedings of the 1st ACM international workshop on Quality of service & security in wireless and mobile networks- 2005.
- [6]. OTran Hoang Hai, Faraz Khan, and Eui-Nam Huh, “**Hybrid Intrusion Detection System for Wireless Sensor Network**”, ICCSA 2007, LNCS 4706, Part II, pp. 383–396, 2007. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 2007
- [7] C. Karlof and D. Wagner, “**Secure routing in wireless sensor networks: Attacks and countermeasures**”, In Proceedings of the 1st IEEE International Workshop on Sensor Network Protocols and Applications (Anchorage, AK, May 11, 2003).
- [8] National Institute of Standards and Technology, “Wireless ad hoc sensor networks”, web: http://w3.antd.nist.gov/wahn_ssn.shtml, retrieved 12th January,2008.
- [9]. Sumit Gupta “Automatic detection of DOS routing attach in Wireless sensor network” MS thesis, Faculty of the Department of Computer Science University of Houston , December 2006
- [10] Rodrigo Roman, Jianying Zhou , Javier Lopez, “**Applying Intrusion Detection Systems to wireless sensor networks**”, Consumer Communications and Networking Conference, 2006. CCNC 2006. 3rd IEEE, 8-10 Jan. 2006 Volume: 1, On page(s): 640- 644 ISBN: 1-4244-0085-6
- [11]. P.Bruth and C. Ko, “ **Challenges in Intrusion detection for wireless ad hoc networks**” in Application and the Internet Workshop =s, 2003 proceedings,2003 Symposium on, PP.368373,2003.

- [12] R. Chadha, G. Lapiotis, S. Wright, “**Policy-Based Networking**”, IEEE Network special issue, March/April 2002, Vol. 16 No. 2, guest editors.
- [13] Linnyer Beatrys RuizJose Marcos Nogueira and Antonio A. F. Loureiro. MANNA: A Management Architecture for Wireless Sensor Networks IEEE Communications Magazine, 2003.2b: http://w3.antd.nist.gov/wahn_ssn.shtml, retrieved 1[68]. Zhou Ying, Xiao Debao, “Mobile agent based Policy management for wireless sensor network”, ISBN: 0-7803-9335-X/05, 2005 IEEE.2th
- [14] W. Chen, N. Jain and S. Singh, “**ANMP: Ad hoc Network Management protocol**”, IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications 17(8) (August 1999) 1506-1531.
- [15] Piya Techateerawat, Andrew Jennings, “**Energy Efficiency of Intrusion Detection Systems in Wireless Sensor Networks**”, Proceedings of the 2006 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Conference on Web Intelligence and Intelligent Agent Technology (WI-IAT 2006 Workshops)(WI-IATW’06) 0-7695-2749-3/06
- [16] O. Kachirski and R. Guha. “**Intrusion Detection Using Mobile Agents in Wireless Ad Hoc Networks**”, Proceeding of the IEEE Workshop on Knowledge Media Networking, pp. 153-158, 2002
- [17] D. R. Raymond and S. F. Midkiff, “**Denial-of-Service in Wireless Sensor Networks: Attacks and Defenses**”, IEEE Pervasive Computing, vol. 7, no. 1, 2008, pp. 74-81.
- [18] V. Bhuse, A. Gupta, “**Anomaly intrusion detection in wireless sensor network**” Journal of High-Speed Networks, Volume 15, Issue 1, pp 33-51, Jan 2006
- [19]. Bharat Bhargava, Weichao Wang. **Visualization of Wormholes in Sensor Networks**. New York, NY, USA: ACM Press, 2004.
- [20] P. Albers et al., “**Security in Ad Hoc Networks: a General Intrusion Detection Architecture Enhancing Trust Based Approaches**,” 1st Int’l. Wksp. Wireless Info. Sys., Ciudad Real, Spain, Apr.3–6, 2002.
- [21] Zhou, L. and Haas, Z. J., “Securing ad hoc networks”, IEEE Network, Volume 13, Issue 6, Nov.-Dec. 1999, pp. 24 – 30. January 2008.
- [22] FZhang, Y. and Lee W “**Intrusion detection in Wireless Ad hoc Networks**”, The 6th annual international conference on Mobile computing and networking, Boston MA, Aug 2000. PP:275-283

NOVEL HYBRID INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM FOR CLUSTERED WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK

Hichem Sedjelmaci¹ and Mohamed Feham¹

**STIC Lab, Department of telecommunications, Abou Bakr Belkaid University,
Tlemcen, Algeria**

ABSTRACT

Wireless sensor network (WSN) is regularly deployed in unattended and hostile environments. The WSN is vulnerable to security threats and susceptible to physical capture. Thus, it is necessary to use effective mechanisms to protect the network. It is widely known, that the intrusion detection is one of the most efficient security mechanisms to protect the network against malicious attacks or unauthorized access. In this paper, we propose a hybrid intrusion detection system for clustered WSN. Our intrusion framework uses a combination between the Anomaly Detection based on support vector machine (SVM) and the Misuse Detection. Experiments results show that most of routing attacks can be detected with low false alarm.

KEYWORDS

Wireless Sensor Network, Hybrid Intrusion Detection System, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Classification Accuracy, False alarm

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0711ijnsa01.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa11_current.html

REFERENCES

- [1] T. H. Hai, F. Khan, and E. N. Huh, “Hybrid Intrusion Detection System for Wireless Sensor Networks”, In Proceeding of the ICCSA, LNCS 4706, pp. 383-396, 2007.
- [2] R. Roman, C. Alcaraz, and J. Lopez, “A Survey of Cryptographic Primitives and Implementations for Hardware-Constrained Sensor Network Nodes”, Mobile Networks and Applications, Springer. Vol.12, no 4, pp 231-244, 2007.
- [3] J. P. Walters, Z.Liang, W.Shi, and V.Chaudhary, “Wireless Sensor Network Security: A Survey”, Security in Distributed Grid and Pervasive Computing, Auerbach Publications, CRC Press, Vol.1, Issue.2, pp.1-50, 2006.
- [4] R. Roman, J. Zhou, and J.Lopez, “Applying Intrusion Detection Systems to Wireless Sensor Networks”, the 3rd IEEE Consumer Communications and Networking Conference pp.640-644, 2006.
- [5] S. Kumar, “Classification and detection of computer intrusions”, PhD Thesis, Department of Computer Sciences, Purdue University, USA, 1995.
- [6] S. Kaplantzis, “Security Models for Wireless Sensor Networks”, PhD Conversion Report, Centre of Telecommunications and Information Engineering, Monash University, Australia, 2006.
- [7] S. Rajasegarar, C. Leckie, and M. Palaniswami, “Detecting Data Anomalies in Wireless Sensor Networks”, Security in Ad hoc and Sensor Network, Computer and Network Security ,World Scientific Publishing Co, Vol. 3, pp.231-259, 2009.
- [8] S. Kaplantzis, A. Shilton, N. Mani, and Y. A. Sekercioglu, “Detecting Selective Forwarding Attacks in Wireless Sensor Networks using Support Vector Machines”, In 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Sensors, Sensor Networks and Information, IEEE, Melbourne, Australia, pp.335-340, 2007.
- [9] K. Flouri, B. B.Lozano, and P. Tsakalides, “Optimal Gossip Algorithm for Distributed Consensus SVM Training in Wireless Sensor Networks”, In Proc.16th International Conference on Digital Signal Processing, IEEE, Santorini, Greece, pp.1-6, 2009.
- [10] K. Flouri, B. B.Lozano, and P. Tsakalides, “Training a SVM-based Classifier in Distributed Sensor Networks”, In Proc.14nd European Signal Processing Conference, Florence, Italy, 2006.
- [11] S.Rajasegarar, C.Leckie, M.Palaniswami, and J. C Bezdek, “Quarter Sphere Based Distributed Anomaly Detection in Wireless Sensor Networks”, In IEEE International Conference on Communications, Glasgow, Scotland, pp.3864-3869, 2007.

- [12] K. Flouri, B. B. Lozano, and P. Tsakalides, “Distributed Consensus Algorithms for SVM Training in Wireless Sensor Networks”, In Proc.16th European Signal Processing Conference, Lausanne,Switzerland, 2008.
- [13] T. H. Hai, E. N. Huh and M. Jo, “A Lightweight Intrusion Detection Framework for Wireless Sensor Networks”, Wireless Communications and mobile computing, Vol.10, Issue.4, pp.559-572, 2010.
- [14] K. Q. Yan, S. C. Wang, S. S. Wang, and C. W. Liu, “Hybrid Intrusion Detection System for Enhancing the Security of a Cluster-based Wireless Sensor Network”,In Proc. 3rd IEEE International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology, Chengdu, China, pp.114-118, 2010.
- [15] G. Huo, and X. Wang, “A Dynamic Model of Intrusion Detection System in Wireless Sensor Networks”, In Proc.International Conference on Information and Automation, IEEE, Zhangjiajie, China, pp.374-378, 2008.
- [16] I. Khalil, S. Bagchi, and N. B. Shroff, “LITEWOP: A Lightweight Countermeasure for the Wormhole Attack in Multihop Wireless Networks”, In Proc. International Conference on Dependable Systems and Networks, IEEE, Yokohama, Japan, pp.612-621, 2005.
- [17] B. Scholkopf, and A. J. Smola, “Learning with Kernels”, The MIT Press, pp.204-205, 2006.
- [18] A. H. Sung, and S. Mukkamala, “Identifying Important Features for Intrusion Detection using Support Vector Machines and Neural Networks”, Symposium on Applications and the Internet, IEEE, Orlando, USA, pp.209-216, 2003.
- [19] W. R. Heinzelman, A. Chandrakasan , and H. Balakrishnan, “Energy Efficient Communication Protocol for Wireless Microsensor Networks”, Proceeding of the 33rd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, IEEE, pp.1-10, 2000.
- [20] S. Lindsey, and C. Raghavendra, “PEGASIS: Power Efficient Gathering in Sensor Information System”, In Proc.IEEE Aerospace conference, vol.3, pp.1125-1130, 2002.
- [21] O. Younis, and S. Fahmy, “Heed: A hybrid, Energy-Efficient Distributed Clustering Approach for Ad Hoc Sensor Networks”, IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, vol.3, No.4, pp.366-379, 2004.
- [22] M. S.Mamun, and A.F.M. Sultanul Kabir, “Hierarchical Design Based Intrusion Detection System For Wireless Ad Hoc Sensor Network”, International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA), Vol.2, No.3, July 2010
- [23] <http://kdd.ics.uci.edu/databases/kddcup99/kddcup99.html>
- [24] A.Stetsko, L.Folkman, and V.Matayáš, “Neighbor-Based Intrusion Detection for Wireless Sensor Network”, 6th International Conference on Wireless and Mobile Communications, IEEE,Valencia, Spain, pp.420-425, 2010.

EXPERIMENTING WITH THE NOVEL APPROACHES IN TEXT STEGANOGRAPHY

Shraddha Dulera¹, Devesh Jinwala¹ and Aroop Dasgupta²

¹Department of Computer Engineering, S V National Institute of Technology, Surat, India

²Bhaskaracharya Institute for Space Applications and Geo-Informatics,
Gandhinagar, India

ABSTRACT

As is commonly known, the steganographic algorithms employ images, audio, video or text files as the medium to ensure hidden exchange of information between multiple contenders to protect the data from the prying eyes. However, using text as the target medium is relatively difficult as compared to the other target media, because of the lack of available redundant information in a text file. In this paper, in the backdrop of the limitations in the prevalent text-based steganographic approaches, we propose simple, yet novel approaches that overcome the same. Our approaches are based on combining the random character sequence and feature coding methods to hide a character. We also analytically evaluate the approaches based on metrics viz. hiding strength, time overhead and memory overhead entailed. As compared to other methods, we believe the approaches proposed impart increased randomness and thus aid higher security at lower overhead.

KEYWORDS

Steganography, Text Steganography, Feature coding

For More Details: <http://aircse.org/journal/nsa/1111nsa16.pdf>

Volume Link: http://aircse.org/journal/jnsa11_current.html

REFERENCES

- [1] M.H. Shirali-Shahreza, “Text steganography by changing words spelling,” Proc. 10th Int. Conf. on Advanced communication technology, 2008, pp. 1912-1913.
- [2] M. Shirali-Shahreza, M. H. Shirali-Shahreza, “Text steganography in SMS,” Proc. Int. Conf. Convergence Information Technology, Washington, 2007, pp. 2260-2265.
- [3] K.F. Rafat, “Enhanced text steganography in SMS,” Proc. of the 2nd Int. Conf. Computer, Control and Communication, Karachi, 2009, pp.1-6.
- [4] M. H. Shirali-Shahreza, M. Shirali-Shahreza, “A new approach to persian/arabic text steganography,” Proc. 5th Int. Conf. Computer and Information Science, Washington, 2006, pp. 310-315.
- [5] J. T. Brassil, S. Low, L. O’Gorman, and N. F. Maxemchuk, “Electronic marking and identification techniques to discourage document copying,” IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, vol. 13, no.8, 1995, pp. 1278-1287.
- [6] W. Bender, D. Gruhl, N.Morimoto, and A Lu, “Techniques for data hiding,” IBM Systems Journal, vol. 35, nos. 3&4, 1996, pp. 313-336.
- [7] A. Gutub, M. M. Fattani, “A Novel Arabic Text Steganography Method Using Points and Extensions,” Proc. of the WASET, 2007, pp. 28-31.
- [8] L. Robert, T.Shanmugapriya, “A study on digital watermarking techniques,” Int. Journal of Recent Trends in Engineering, vol.1, no.2, May 2009.
- [9] K. Alla and R.S.R. Prasad., “An evolution of hindi text steganography,” Proc. of the 6th Int. Conf. Information Technology: New Generations, Washington, 2009, pp. 1577-1578.

A HIERARCHICAL INTRUSION DETECTION ARCHITECTURE FOR WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

Hossein Jadidoleslamy

**Department of Information Technology, Anzali International Branch, The University
of Guilan, Rasht, Iran**

ABSTRACT

Networks protection against different types of attacks is one of most important posed issue into the network and information security application domains. This problem on Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), in attention to their special properties, has more importance. Now, there are some of proposed architectures and guide lines to protect Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) against different types of intrusions; but any one of them do not has a comprehensive view to this problem and they are usually designed and implemented in single-purpose; but, the proposed design in this paper tries to has been a comprehensive view to this issue by presenting a complete and comprehensive Intrusion Detection Architecture (IDA). The main contribution of this architecture is its hierarchical structure; i.e., it is designed and applicable, in one or two levels, consistent to the application domain and its required security level. Focus of this paper is on the clustering WSNs, designing and deploying Cluster-based Intrusion Detection System (CIDS) on cluster-heads and Wireless Sensor Network wide level Intrusion Detection System (WSNIDS) on the central server. Suppositions of the WSN and Intrusion Detection Architecture (IDA) are: static and heterogeneous network, hierarchical and clustering structure, clusters' overlapping and using hierarchical routing protocol such as LEACH, but along with minor changes. Finally, the proposed idea has been verified by designing a questionnaire, representing it to some (about 50 people) experts and then, analyzing and evaluating its acquired results.

KEYWORDS

Wireless Sensor Network (WSN), Security, Routing, Intrusion Detection System (IDS), Attack, Detection, Response & Tracking.

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0312nsa08.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa12_current.html

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Mohammadi, R. A. Ebrahimi and H. Jadidoleslami; [A Comparison of Routing Attacks on Wireless Sensor Networks](#); Journal of Information Assurance and Security (JIAS); ISSN 1554-1010 Volume 6, pp. 195-215; 2011.
- [2] S. Mohammadi, R. A. Ebrahimi and H. Jadidoleslami; [A Comparison of Link Layer Attacks on Wireless Sensor Networks](#); Journal of Information Security (JIS); 2011.
- [3] K. Sharma and M. K. Ghose; [Wireless Sensor Networks: An Overview on its Security Threats](#); IJCA, Special Issue on “Mobile Ad-hoc Networks” MANETs; CSE Department, SMIT, Sikkim, India; 2010.
- [4] T. A. Zia; [A Security Framework for Wireless Sensor Networks](#); Doctor of Philosophy Thesis; The School of Information Technologies, University of Sydney; Feb 2008.
- [5] M. Saxena; [Security in Wireless Sensor Networks: A Layer-based Classification](#); Department of Computer Science, Purdue University.
- [6] Z. Li and G. Gong; [A Survey on Security in Wireless Sensor Networks](#); Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Waterloo, Canada.
- [7] A. Dimitrievski, V. Pejovska and D. Davcev; [Security Issues and Approaches in WSN](#); Department of computer science, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology; Skopje, Republic of Macedonia.
- [8] J. Yick, B. Mukherjee and D. Ghosal; [Wireless Sensor Network Survey](#); Elsevier’s Computer Networks Journal 52 (2292- 2330); Department of Computer Science, University of California; 2008.
- [9] C. Karlof and D. Wagner; [Secure Routing in Wireless Sensor Networks: Attacks and Countermeasures](#); Elsevier’s AdHoc Networks Journal, Special Issue on Sensor Network Applications and Protocols; In First IEEE International Workshop on Sensor Network Protocols and Applications; University of California at Berkeley, Berkeley, USA; 2003.
- [10] A. Perrig, R. Szewczyk, V. Wen, D. Culler and D. Tygar; [SPINS: Security Protocols for Sensor Networks](#); [Wireless Networking ACM CCS](#); 2003.
- [11] B. Krishnamachari, D. Estrin, and S. Wicker; [The Impact of Data Aggregation in Wireless Sensor Networks](#); [International Workshop on Distributed Event-Based Systems, \(DEBS ’02\)](#), p 457-458; 2002.
- [12] V. Handziski, A. Koppke, H. Karl, C. Frank, and W. Drytkiewicz; [Improving The Energy Efficiency of Directed Diffusion Using Passive Clustering](#); in [Proc. 1st European Workshop on Wireless Sensor Networks](#), pp. 172 – 187, Berlin, Germany; 2004.

- [13] K. Scarfone and P. Mell; [Guide to Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems \(IDPS\)](#); NIST 800-94; Feb 2007.
- [14] G. Maselli, L. Deri and S. Suin; [Design and Implementation of an Anomaly Detection System: an Empirical Approach](#); University of Pisa, Italy; 2002.
- [15] V. Chandala, A. Banerjee and V. Kumar; [Anomaly Detection: A Survey](#); *ACM Computing Surveys*; University of Minnesota; Sep 2009.
- [16] Ch. Krügel and Th. Toth; [A Survey on Intrusion Detection Systems](#); TU Vienna , Austria; 2000.
- [17] J. Molina and M. Cukier; [Evaluating Attack Resiliency for Host Intrusion Detection Systems](#); *Information Assurance and Security Journal*; 2009.
- [18] S. Selliah; [Mobile Agent-Based Attack Resistant Architecture for Distributed Intrusion Detection System](#); MSc Thesis, College of Engineering and Mineral Resources at West Virginia University; 2001.
- [19] A. K. Jones and R. S. Sielken; [Computer System Intrusion Detection: A Survey](#); University of Virginia, USA.
- [20] S. Northcutt and J. Novak; [Network Intrusion Detection: An Analyst's Handbook](#); New Riders Publishing; Thousand Oaks, CA, USA; 2002.
- [21] S. Zanero and S. M. Savaresi; [Unsupervised Learning Techniques for an Intrusion Detection System](#); *ACM Symposium on Applied Computing*; 2004.
- [22] O. Depren, M. Topallar, E. narim and M. K. Ciliz; [An Intelligent Intrusion Detection System \(IDS\) for Anomaly and Misuse Detection in Computer Networks](#); 2005.
- [23] R. A. Kemmerer and G. Vigna; [Intrusion Detection: A Brief History and Overview](#); 2002.

FORTIFICATION OF HYBRID INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM USING VARIANTS OF NEURAL NETWORKS AND SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINES

A. M. Chandrashekhar¹ and K. Raghuveer²

¹Department of Computer Science, Sri Jayachamarajendra College of Engineering (SJCE), Mysore, Karnataka, 570006, India

²Department of Information Science, National Institute of Engineering (NIE), Mysore, Karnataka 57008, India

ABSTRACT

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) form a key part of system defence, where it identifies abnormal activities happening in a computer system. In recent years different soft computing based techniques have been proposed for the development of IDS. On the other hand, intrusion detection is not yet a perfect technology. This has provided an opportunity for data mining to make quite a lot of important contributions in the field of intrusion detection. In this paper we have proposed a new hybrid technique by utilizing data mining techniques such as fuzzy C means clustering, Fuzzy neural network / Neurofuzzy and radial basis function(RBF) SVM for fortification of the intrusion detection system. The proposed technique has five major steps in which, first step is to perform the relevance analysis, and then input data is clustered using Fuzzy C-means clustering. After that, neuro-fuzzy is trained, such that each of the data point is trained with the corresponding neuro-fuzzy classifier associated with the cluster. Subsequently, a vector for SVM classification is formed and in the last step, classification using RBFSVM is performed to detect intrusion has happened or not. Data set used is the KDD cup 1999 dataset and we have used precision, recall, F-measure and accuracy as the evaluation metrics parameters. Our technique could achieve better accuracy for all types of intrusions. The results of proposed technique are compared with the other existing techniques. These comparisons proved the effectiveness of our technique.

KEYWORDS

Intrusion Detection System, Fuzzy C-Means Clustering, fuzzy neural network, Support Vector Machine

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0113nsa06.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa13_current.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Ghanshyam Prasad Dubey, Prof. Neetesh Gupta and Rakesh K Bhujade, “A Novel Approach to Intrusion Detection System using Rough Set Theory and Incremental SVM”, International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering (IJSCE), vol.1, no.1, pp.14-18, 2011.
- [2] Iftikhar Ahmad, Azween Abdullah and Abdullah Alghamdi, (2010) “Towards the selection of best neural network system for intrusion detection”, International Journal of the Physical Sciences, vol.5, no.2, pp.1830-1839.
- [3] J.T. Yao, S.L. Zhao, L. V. Saxton (2005), “A study on fuzzy intrusion detection”, Proc. of Data Mining, Intrusion Detection, Information Assurance, and Data Networks Security SPIE. 5812, pp. 23-30.
- [4] Hansung Lee, Jiyoung Song, and Daihee Park (2005), “Intrusion Detection System Based on Multi-class SVM”, Dept. of computer & Information Science, Korea Univ., Korea, pp. 511–519.
- [5] David Wagner and Paolo Soto (2002), “Mimicry Attacks on Host Based Intrusion Detection Systems” Proceedings of the 9th ACM conference on Computer and communications security, pp. 255 – 264.
- [6] Rung-Ching Chen and Su-Ping Chen (2008), “Intrusion detection using a hybrid support vectormachine based on entropy and tf-idf”, International Journal of Innovative Computing, Information and Control, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 41301-424.
- [7] Srinivas Mukkamala, Andrew H. Sung, Ajith Abraham and Vitorino Ramos(2004), “Intrusion detection systems using adaptive regression splines”, In Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems, ICEIS, vol.3, pp.26-33.
- [8] Snehal A. Mulay, P.R. Devale and G.v. Garje (2010), “Intrusion Detection System using Support Vector Machine and Decision Tree”, International Journal of Computer Applications, vol 3, no 3, pp. 40-43.
- [9] Deepak Tinguriya and Binod Kumar (2010), “A Effect Approach for Intrusion Detection System using Incremental SVM”, BLB-International Journal of Science & Technology, vol.1, no.2, pp.127-134.
- [10] Ajith Abraham, Ravi Jainb, Johnson Thomas and Sang Yong Han (2007), “D-SCIDS: Distributed soft computing intrusion detection system”, Journal of Network and Computer Applications, vol. 30, pp. 81–98.
- [11] D. E. Denning (1987), “An intrusion detection model,” IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 222–232.
- [12] S. Kumar and E. Spafford (1995), “A software Architecture to Support Misuse Intrusion Detection”, 18th National Information Security Conference, pp.194-204.

- [13] Hu W, Liao Y and Vemuri V (2003). “Robust support vector machines for anomaly detection in computer security“, In Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications, pp. 23-24.
- [14] Peddabachigari S, Abraham A, Grosan C (2007), “Modelling intrusion detection system using hybrid intelligent systems. Journal of Network and Computer Applications, vol.30, no.1, pp.114–132.
- [15] Chengjie Gu, Shunyi Zhang and Xiaozhen Xue (2011), “Network Intrusion Detection Based on Improved Proximal SVM”, Advances in Information Sciences and Service Sciences. Vol 3, no. 4, pp.132-140. International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA), Vol.5, No.1, January 2013 89
- [16] S.Ganapathy, N.Jaisankar, P.Yogesh and A. Kannan (2011), “An Intelligent Intrusion Detection System Using Outlier Detection and Multiclass SVM”, International Journal on Recent Trends in Engineering & Technology, vol.05, no.01, 2011.
- [17] Mansour Sheikhan and Amir Khalili (2010), ” Intrusion Detection Based on Rule Extraction from Dynamic Cell Structure Neural Networks“, Majlesi Journal of Electrical Engineering, Vol. 4, No. 4, pp. 24-34.
- [18] Kyaw Thet Khaing (2010), “Enhanced Features ranking and Selection using Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) and k-Nearest Neighbour Algorithms in Support Vector Machine for Intrusion Detection System“, International Journal of Network and Mobile Technologies, Vol.1, No.1, pp. 8-14.
- [19] Arvind Mewada, Prafful Gedam, Shamaila Khan and M. Udayapal Reddy (2010), “Network Intrusion Detection Using Multiclass Support Vector Machine”, Special Issue of IJCCT for International Conference [ACCTA-2010], Vol.1, No.2,3,4, pp.172-175.
- [20] Snehal A, Mulay P.R, Devale G.V, and Garje(2010), “Intrusion Detection System Using Support Vector Machine and Decision Tree”, International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol.3, No.3, pp.40–43.
- [21] Gang Wang, Jinxing Hao, Jian Ma and Lihua Huang (2010), “A new approach to intrusion detection using Artificial Neural Networks and fuzzy clustering“, Expert Systems with Applications, pp. 1-8.
- [22] Muna Mhammad T. Jawhar and Monica Mehrotra (2010), “Design Network Intrusion Detection System using hybrid Neuro-fuzzy”, International Journal of Computer Science and Security, Vol.4, No.3, pp.285-294.
- [23] Ghadiri A and Ghadiri N (2011), ” An Adaptive Hybrid Architecture for Intrusion Detection Based on Fuzzy Clustering and RBF Neural Networks“, In Proceedings of the Ninth Annual Communication Networks and Services Research Conference (CNSR), pp. 123 – 129.

[24] Pohsiang Tsai, Tich Phuoc Tran, Tony Jan and Xiaoying Kong, “Network Intrusion Detection using Machine Learning and Voting techniques”, Machine Learning, pp.267-290, 2010.

[25] “DARPA Intrusion Detection Evaluation Data Set”
from <http://www.ll.mit.edu/mission/communications/ist/corpora/ideval/data/1998data.html>

[26] “KDDCup1999 Data”
from <http://www.sigkdd.org/kddcup/index.php?section=1999&method=data>

[27] Mahbod Tavallaee, Ebrahim Bagheri, Wei Lu and Ali A. Ghorbani (2009), “A detailed analysis of the KDD CUP 99 data set“, in Proceedings of the Second IEEE international conference on Computational intelligence for security and defence applications, pp. 53-58, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada.

[28] C. Elkan(2000),“Results of the KDD’99 Classifier Learning”, SIGKDD Explorations, ACM SIGKDD.

[29] Mahesh kumar sabhanani and gursel Serpen (2003), “Application of Machine learning algorithms to KDD intrusion detection dataset within misuse detection context” In Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning, Models, Technologies and Applications (MLMTA), Vol. 1, pp. 209-215.

[30] J. C. Dunn (1973): “A Fuzzy Relative of the ISODATA Process and Its Use in Detecting Compact Well-Separated Clusters“, Journal of Cybernetics, Vol. 3, pp.32-57.

[31] Jose Vieira, Fernando Morgado Dias and Alexandre Mota (2004), “Neuro-Fuzzy Systems: A Survey“, In proceedings of 5th WSEAS NNA International Conference on Neural Networks and Applications.

[32] R. Jang (1992), “Neuro-Fuzzy Modelling: Architectures, Analysis and Applications”, PhD Thesis, University of California, Berkley.

MULTI-STAGE FILTER USING ENHANCED ADABOOST FOR NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION

P.Natesan, and P.Balasubramanie

**Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
Kongu Engineering College, Perundurai, Erode 638 052, Tamilnadu, India**

ABSTRACT

Based on the analysis and distribution of network attacks in KDDCup99 dataset and real time traffic, this paper proposes a design of multi stage filter which is an efficient and effective approach in dealing with various categories of attacks in networks. The first stage of the filter is designed using Enhanced Adaboost with Decision tree algorithm to detect the frequent attacks occurs in the network and the second stage of the filter is designed using enhanced Adaboost with Naïve Byes algorithm to detect the moderate attacks occurs in the network. The final stage of the filter is used to detect the infrequent attack which is designed using the enhanced Adaboost algorithm with Naïve Bayes as a base learner. Performance of this design is tested with the KDDCup99 dataset and is shown to have high detection rate with low false alarm rates.

KEYWORDS

Enhanced Adaboost, multi-stage filter, decision tree, Naive Bayes classification, detection rate, false alarm rate.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0512nsa08.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa12_current.html

REFERENCES

1. Xuan Dau Hoang, Jiankun Hu, and Peter Bertok, “A program-based anomaly intrusion detection scheme using multiple detection engines and fuzzy inference,” *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, Vol. 32, pp. 1219-1228, 2009.
2. P. Garcia-Teodoro, J. Diaz-Verdejo, G. Macia-Fernandez, and E.Vazquez, “Anomaly-based network intrusion detection: Techniques, systems and challenges,” *Computers & Security*, Vol. 28, pp. 18-28, 2009.
3. Weiming Hu, Wei Hu and Steve Maybank, “AdaBoost-Based Algorithm for Network Intrusion Detection,” *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, Vol. 38, pp. 577-583, April2008.
4. N. B. Amor, S. Benferhat, and Z. Elouedi, “Naïve Bayes vs. decision trees in intrusion detection systems,” In Proc. of the 2004 ACM Symposium on Applied Computing, New York, pp. 420- 424, 2004.
5. Dewan Md. Farid, Nouria Harbi and Mohammad Zahidur Rahman, “Combining naive bayes and decision tree for adaptive intrusion detection”, *International Journal of Network Security & its Applications*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 12 – 25, 2010.
6. Natesan P, Balasubramanie P and Gowrison G, “Adaboost with Single and Compound weak classifier in Network Intrusion Detection”, In Proceedings of International conference on Advanced computing, Networking & Security”, Vol. 1, pp 282-290, Dec-2011.
7. Xiang C, Yong PC, Meng, “Design of multiple-level hybrid classifier for intrusion detection system using Bayesian clustering and decision trees”. *Pattern Recognition Letters* 29(7):918–924, 2008.
8. Gupta KK, Nath B (2010) Layered approach using conditional random fields for intrusion detection. *IEEE Trans Dependable Secure Computing* 7(1):35–49, 2010.
9. Kok-Chin Khor, Choo-Yee Ting and Somnuk Phon-Amnuaisuk A, “cascaded classifier approach for improving detection rates on rare attack categories in network intrusion detection“, *Journal of Applied Intelligence*, DOI 10.1007/s10489-010-0263-y.
10. Natesan P, Balasubramanie P and Gowrison G, “Design of two stage filter using enhanced Adaboost for improving attack detection rates in network intrusion detection”, *Journal of Computer science, Information technology and Security*, Vol.2, No.2, pp. 349-357.
11. KDDCup99 Dataset, <http://kdd.ics.uci.edu/databases/kddcup99/kddcup99.html>. 1999.
12. Z.Pawlak, “Rough sets”, *International Journal of Computer and Information Sciences*, Vol.11, No. 5, pp. 341-356, 1982.

13. Lei Shi, Li Zhang, Xinming Ma and Xiaohong Hu, “[Rough set Based Personalized Recommendation in Mobile Commerce](#). 2009 International conference on Active Media Technology”, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 370-375, 2009.
14. Sabhnani, M. R., & Serpen, G. [Application of machine learning algorithms to KDD intrusion detection dataset with in misuse detection context](#). In Proceedings of the international conference on machine learning: Models, technologies, and applications. pp. 209–215, 2003.
15. Xuren, W., Famei, H., & Rongsheng, X. [Modeling intrusion detection system by discovering association rule in rough set theory framework](#). In Proceedings of the international conference on computational intelligence for modeling control and automation, and international conference on intelligent agents. Web Technologies and Internet Commerce (CIMCAIAWTIC’06), 2006.
16. J.W. Han and M.Kamber, [Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques](#), 2nd edition. Morgan Kaufmann, pp. 310-318, 2006.
17. N.Friedman, D.Geiger and M.Goldsmidt, “[Bayesian Network Classifiers](#),” Machine Learning, Vol.29, pp 131-163, Nov 1997.
18. Yoav Freund, Robert E.Schapire. “[A Decision theoretic generalization of on-line learning and an application to boosting](#),” Journal of Computer and System Sciences. Vol. 55, 119-139, 1997.
19. P.N. Tan, [Introduction to Data Mining](#). Reading, MA:Addison-Wesley, 2006.
20. Shi-Jinn Horng, Ming-Yang Su, Yuan-Hsin Chen, Tzong-Wann kao, Rong-Jian Chen, Jui-Lin Lai, Citra Dwi Perkasa, “[A novel intrusion detection system based on hierarchical clustering and International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications \(IJNSA\)](#), Vol.4, No.3, May 2012 [135 support vector machines](#)”, Expert Systems with Applications, Vol.38, pp.306-313, 2010, DOI:10.1016/j.eswa.2010.06.066.
21. Pfahringer, B. [Winning the KDD99 classification cup: Bagged boosting SIGKDD Explorations](#),1(2), 65–66, 2000.

STATISTICAL QUALITY CONTROL APPROACHES TO NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION

Rohitha Goonatilake¹, Rafic Bachnak¹, and Susantha Herath²

**¹Department of Engineering, Mathematics, and Physics Texas A&M International
University, TX 78041, USA**

²Department of Information Systems, St. Cloud State University, MN 56301, USA

ABSTRACT

In the study of network intrusion, much attention has been drawn to on-time detection of intrusion to safeguard public and private interest and to capture the law-breakers. Even though various methods have been found in literature, some situations warrant us to determine intrusions of network in real-time to prevent further undue harm to the computer network as and when they occur. This approach helps detect the intrusion and has a greater potential to apprehend the law-breaker. The purpose of this article is to formulate a method to this effect that is based on the statistical quality control techniques widely used in the manufacturing and production processes.

KEYWORDS

Anomalies, control charts, false alarm, intrusion, network system, and quality control

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/1111nsa08.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa11_current.html

REFERENCES

- [1] James C. Reynolds, James Just, Larry Clough, and Ryan Maglich, "On-Line Intrusion Detection and Attack Prevention Using Diversity, Generate-and-Test, and Generalization," Proceedings of the 36th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS'03), 2002, pp. 1-8
- [2] L. Ertoz, E. Eilertson, A. Lazarevic, P. Tan, P. Dokas, V. Kumar, and J. Srivastava, "Next Generation Data Mining," The MINDS – Minnesota Intrusion Detection System, MIT Press, 2004
- [3] Vipin Kumar, "Parallel and Distributed Computing for Cybersecurity," IEEE Distributed Systems Online, 2005, Vol. 6, No. 10
- [4] William Stallings "Cryptography and Network Security: Principles and Practice," 3rd Edition, Prentice Hall, 2003
- [5] <http://www.kernelthread.com/publications/security/intrusion.html>
- [6] Sheldon M. Ross, "Introduction to Probability and Statistics for Engineers and Scientists," Fourth Edition, Elsevier Academic Press, 2009
- [7] Arunabha Mukhopadhyay, Samir Chatterjee, Debashis Saha, Ambuj Mahanti, and Samir K. Sadhukhna, "e-Risk Management with Insurance: A Framework using Copula aided Bayesian Belief Networks," Proceedings of the 39th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 2006, pp. 1-6
- [8] Alec Pawling, Nitesh V. Chawla, and Greg Madey, "Anomaly Detection in a Mobile Communication Network," Comput Math Organ Theory, 2007, Vol. 13, pp. 407-422
- [9] Paul E. Proctor "The Practical Intrusion Detection Handbook", Prentice Hall, 2001
- [10] H. D. Brunk, "An introduction to Mathematical Statistics," Ginn and Co, New York, 1960
- [11] Nong Ye, Syed Masum Emran, Qiang Chen, and Sean Vilbert, "Multivariate Statistical Analysis of Audit Trails for Host-Based Intrusion Detection," IEEE Transactions on Computers, 2002, Vol. 51, No. 7
- [12] Nong Ye and Qiang Chen, "An Anomaly Detection Technique Based On a Chi-Square Statistic for Detecting Intrusions into Information Systems," Quality and Reliability Engineering International, 2001, Vol. 17, pp. 105–112
- [13] Petar Čisar and Sanja Maravić Čisar, "Quality Control in Function of Statistical Anomaly Detection in Intrusion Detection Systems," 4th Serbian-Hungarian Joint Symposium on Intelligent Systems (SISY 2006), 2006, pp. 209-220

[14] Rohitha Goonatilake, Ajantha Herath, Suvineetha Herath, Susantha Herath, and Jayantha Herath, "Intrusion Detection Using the Chi-Square Goodness-of-Fit Test for Information Assurance, Network, Forensics and Software Security," The Journal of Computing Sciences in Colleges (JCSC), Vol. 23, No. 1, 2007, pp. 255-263

[15] CengizKahraman, "Fuzzy Applications in Industrial Engineering," Springer-Verlag, 2006

[16] P. Rama Murthy, "Production and Operations Management," Revised Second Edition, New Age International Publisher, 2007

[17] CengizKahraman and MesutYavuz, "Production Engineering and Management under Fuzziness," Springer, 2010

[18] Angel R. Otero, Carlos E. Otero, and AbrarQureshi, "A Multi-Criteria Evaluation of Information Security Controls Using Boolean Features," International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA), Vol.2, No.4, 2010